

Template for Institute Policy for Research Data and Software Management

Aims

The field of research data management (RDM) and research software management (RSM) is developing at a rapid pace, resulting in a growing necessity for research institutes to stay up-to-date with changes in university policies and developments in the practices of doing research. This template is therefore provided by the Digital Competence Centre (DCC) as a way to help data stewards when they are renewing their institute's RDM/RSM policy. Throughout this document, we'll refer to *research data management* for readability purposes, but this should be understood to include research software management too. If needed, this can be made more explicit by the data steward. We have provided text regarding the following topics:

- Definitions
- Data Management Plan (DMP) / Software Management Plan (SMP)
- Storing and sharing
- Archiving and publishing
- Personal data
- Ethics and informed consent
- Support and training

Various fonts are used throughout the template, with different meanings:

BLUE FONT (in uppercase)	This indicates that something needs to be replaced or gives instructions.
Blue font (in lowercase)	This requires a choice . This often has to do with institutional requirements and views. Further, for many sections we have listed several options that research institutes can choose from. Research institutes are not limited to these options, but these are options that are recommended by the Radboud University and in line with the RU RDM policy.
Bold red font	These are keywords that help the reader quickly find relevant sections.
Bold black font	These are indicators where something must be done by the researcher.

Questions

Please do not hesitate to contact us if:

- You have any questions regarding this template.
- You have any questions about the RU RDM policy.
- You would like assistance with your institute's RDM policy.

We can be reached via e-mail at dcc@ru.nl. We also strongly recommend that data stewards contact their Faculty's [local privacy officer](#) to reach consensus on the sections on personal data, the data protection impact assessments, and the anonymisation of research data.

Over the course of its creation this template has seen significant improvements thanks to the efforts of several people that we as DCC would like to thank for their contribution including the Open Science Officer, the Research Policy Officer, and two Privacy Officers.

Radboud University INSTITUTE NAME's Policy for Research Data and Software Management

Approved by: NAME OF INDIVIDUAL(S) WHO APPROVED THE RDM POLICY

Written by: AUTHOR NAME, Data Steward

VERSION NUMBER, DATE

Optional: PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER

Optional: Cite as: SPECIFY HOW TO CITE THIS DOCUMENT

Commented [KM1]: We like to encourage FAIR in our own work and therefore would recommend that institutes register their policies in FAIRsharing: <https://fairsharing.org/search?fairsharingRegistry=Policy> Once registered in FAIRsharing, you will receive a DOI. This is encouraged by FAIR IMPACT, openaire and EOSC.

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RDM requirements at INSTITUTE NAME

- **Contact the data steward** at [EMAIL ADDRESS](#) or [PHONE NUMBER](#) with any questions regarding research data management.

Before research

- Write a **data or software management plan** and **request feedback** by logging in [here](#) and using the **SPECIFY FORMAT: General RU DMP format / INSTITUTE's NAME DMP format / General RU Software Management Plan**.
 - Before deciding to collect data for your project, see if there are data that you can **reuse**.
- If processing **personal data**:
 - Follow the GDPR throughout the entirety of the research process.
 - Contact the **local privacy officer / local privacy coordinator** here [LINK TO LOCAL PRIVACY OFFICER / LOCAL PRIVACY COORDINATOR](#) before the data collection has started to fill out a **pre-DPIA** (Data Protection Impact Assessment) if processing personal data.
- Check [LINK TO ETHICS COMMITTEE WEBSITE](#) to see if the research proposal needs to be reviewed by the **NAME OF ETHICS COMMITTEE**.
- Check [the Digital Competence Centre on gROW](#) to see what **RDM courses** are relevant for you.

During research

- **Store and share** research data and software using the [Radboud Data Repository / Microsoft 365 Team / workgroup folder / SURFfilesender or / other option](#) here [INSERT LINK\(S\)](#).
- If you produce research software,
 - It is **recommended / required** to use a **version control system**: [FILL IN SPECIFIC VERSION CONTROL SYSTEM IF APPLICABLE](#).
 - It is required to add **documentation**.

After research

- **Archive or publish** research data/software in the [Radboud Data Repository \(RDR\) / NAME OF OTHER REPOSITORY](#) for a minimum of ten years accompanied by sufficient metadata and documentation. You can link your online version control repository to the software or data collection in the [RDR / NAME OF OTHER REPOSITORY](#).
- Use **CC0 / OTHER APPROPRIATE license** when publishing the research data and **Apache 2.0 / OTHER APPROPRIATE license** when publishing the research software unless there are legal or ethical constraints.
- **Register the archived or published dataset/software** in Radboud University's Research Information Services (RIS) [here](#), **unless it was archived with public metadata or published in the Radboud Data Repository, in which case this happens automatically**.
 - Link your datasets / software to related associated publications.
 - Use of your ORCID is highly encouraged.
- **Store other forms of research-related data**, that are not suited for archiving in a repository (e.g. consent forms and encrypted keyfiles), in a [workgroup folder / OTHER LOCATION](#) here [LINK TO LOCATION](#).

Commented [HB2]: Feel free to add your own institute specific RDM course programs here (if available).

The Chart of Guidance

This Chart of Guidance allows you to find the external resources, websites and contact info for the various people, organisations and services involved with research data and software management.

Commented [KM3]: The aim of this "Chart of Guidance" is to direct researchers to most used links they will use, as reflected in the Institute's RDM Policy for RDM. As with the whole document, feel free to adapt and use this as it fits your needs.

Definitions

For whom this policy is intended

The **INSTITUTE NAME**'s Policy for Research Data and Software Management (hereafter referred to as this policy) applies to all research data and software collected/developed or reused by employees and all persons affiliated with the Radboud University. This means that this policy is not intended for **SPECIFY WHO: external collaborators from other institutes or universities**. However, it does apply to **SPECIFY WHO: external PhDs / student-assistants / emeritus professors**.

This policy does not replace, but rather expands upon the [Radboud University Research data management policy](#)¹ (hereafter referred to as RU RDM policy) and the [Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#).

Roles and responsibilities

The roles and responsibilities for good research data management are outlined in [Tasks and responsibilities in research data management at Radboud University](#). At the institutional level this responsibility is shared between the Director of Research, the data steward, and the researcher.

The **Director of Research** is responsible for the development, implementation, and compliance of this policy. Among other tasks, the **data steward** is responsible for providing first line research data management support to researchers and assists in the compliance with this RDM Policy within the institute and monitors this compliance within the institute.

All **researchers** are responsible for effective and accurate data and software management and must therefore familiarise themselves and adhere to this policy. **PhD candidates** must additionally adhere to the [Radboud University Doctorate regulations](#) and are responsible for the data they collect for their dissertation, together with their supervisors.

Compliance with policy

The data steward will monitor compliance with this institutional policy by [randomly selecting a subset and checking the compliance with safe storage locations / filling out of data management plans / repositories used for archiving and publishing, etc.](#) In case of non-compliance, the data steward informs the [board / Director of Research](#). Together they can decide which actions are necessary to address this non-compliance. **SPECIFY POSSIBLE CONSEQUENCES**.

INSTITUTE NAME will review and revise this policy in consultation with the Radboud University Digital Competence Centre every **INSERT TIME: two years**.

Control of research data

In general, as outlined in the [Radboud University Guidelines on control of research data](#), research data generated by employees is controlled by Radboud University. This means that Radboud University is authorised to exercise their rights to this research data. When research data is generated in collaboration with other institutions or externally funded, other arrangements may exist. If it is not clear to the researcher who controls the research data or if the researcher has any questions, they should contact [Administration & Legal Affairs](#).

¹ As this policy expands upon the Radboud University Research data management policy, we have incorporated text and sections from the RU RDM policy here.

Research data

The definition of research data includes:

All information, digital and non-digital, that was generated during the research process and used to form scientific conclusions. This encompasses information that is used for forming and testing hypotheses as well as information upon which conclusions are based. If the information contributed to results in a scientific report, it is research data². At [INSTITUTE NAME](#), typical data takes the form of:

- Empirical data
- Simulated data
- Stimuli for experiments
- Audio/video recordings
- Questionnaires
- Methodologies
- Models
- Observation reports
- Structures literature searches
- Transcripts

Research software

Research software can be defined as “source code files, algorithms, scripts, computational workflows and executables that were created during the research process or for a research purpose” (Gruenpeter et al., 2021, p.16).

At [INSTITUTE NAME](#), typical software takes the form of:

- Analysis script
- Software package
- Computational environment
- OTHER

Commented [HB4]: This is an example of different types of data. We recommend that you adjust this list so that it includes the types of research data that are most common in your research institute. That way it mirrors the data that researchers are familiar with.

Research data and software management

As the name indicates, research data management (RDM) is the responsible management of research data along the research life cycle (see Figure 1 and the [Appendix](#)). RDM includes a variety of activities such as planning, collecting, processing, analysing, archiving, and publishing.

Having good RDM has **many advantages**. It allows the researcher to make informed decisions about the research data and helps to keep the research project organised. This means that the researcher can keep the data safe, prevent unauthorised access, and avoid data loss. Moreover, the researcher can save time, conform to standards of scientific integrity, comply with policies, and adhere to open science principles. Lastly, good RDM encourages the reuse of data and presents improved prospects for recognition of good research practices and accountability.

Figure 1: Research Data Lifecycle

² The definition of research data was inspired by the definition provided in the [Radboud Data Repository](#).

Software management also often plays an important role in the research process. The development of software can be the main research output (see Figure 2). In other cases, software is used for the processing and analysis of data (see Figure 1: Data processing and analysis). One of the advantages of research software management is that good documentation, archiving, publishing, and version control make it possible to reuse the software later, both by the original team and by others. Version control also helps prevent software from being lost and allows researchers to return to earlier versions whenever needed.

Figure 2: Research Software Lifecycle based on Infrastructures for Quality Research Software (RSQKit Community, 2025)

Open Science

Open Science³, is a movement that promotes open and collaborative research, resulting in academic outputs that are increasingly made available as openly as possible. This encourages data reuse and contributes to greater scientific and societal impact. Open Science is becoming more prominent in research. By practicing Open Science, research becomes more reliable and transparent. Good RDM can contribute to Open Science and make data as open as possible by encouraging researchers to follow associated practices from an early stage in the research data lifecycle.

Reuse of data

Radboud University researchers are encouraged to reuse research data whenever possible. When they do, they must cite said data in the scientific literature that is based on that data.

In the spirit of Open Science, Radboud University researchers are encouraged to reuse research data and software whenever possible. Reusing data and software can save time and money, reduces the burden on participants, and fosters the open science principles.

In [LIST FIELD NAMES IN INSTUTUTE](#), researchers can find data to reuse at the following repositories: [LIST REPOSITORIES](#). In [LIST FIELD NAMES IN INSTUTUTE](#), researchers can find software to reuse at the following repositories: [LIST REPOSITORIES](#).

If looking for more generic repositories, researchers can find tips on how to find a reliable repository [here](#). When reusing data or software, the researcher must respect any intellectual property rights and comply with the user terms.

Furthermore, when reusing data or software, researchers must **cite** said data in any scientific literature based on the data to ensure that the researchers of the data are properly acknowledged. Citations should allow for identification of, access to, and verification of the specific data or software that supports a claim.

³ For more information on Open Science in the Netherlands, see NWO's [website](#).

This means that the citations must at least include title, author(s), publication year, persistent identifier, publisher, and if applicable: version number and resource type (e.g. dataset, software).

Data Management Plan (DMP)

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is mandatory for all research projects that generate new research data, or that reuse existing data in ways that require additional research data management decisions, risk assessments, or agreements.

A data management plan (DMP) is a dynamic document that the researcher develops at the start of a research project. A DMP describes the whole research life cycle, allowing the researcher to plan how research data will be handled during each phase of the research life cycle. A DMP ensures that data are well-organised, secure, and aligned with FAIR principles, thereby strengthening the quality and impact of the research. It also supports researchers in estimating RDM-related costs and incorporating these into funding applications. In addition, a DMP facilitates early consideration of ethical approvals, privacy assessments, and any required legal or contractual arrangements. If you are writing code for the processing or analysis of the data, it is recommended that some information on this is included in the DMP. If your main output is research software, see the section below on [Software Management Plan](#).

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is mandatory for all research projects that generate new research data, or that reuse existing data in ways that require additional research data management decisions, risk assessments, or agreements. A DMP must be prepared before the start of data collection or data acquisition and must be kept up to date throughout the project. This can be done by logging in to [Research Information Services](#) and using the [INSTITUTE NAME's](#) template. **SPECIFY WHO:** All researchers are additionally **required / recommended** to request feedback on their DMP from their data steward. Updated versions of a DMP **can / must** receive additional feedback. The aim is to provide the researcher with feedback within **SPECIFY TIME: five** working days.

Software Management Plan (SMP)

A Software Management Plan has similar advantages as a Data Management Plan but is specifically developed for research projects that have research software as main research output. At [INSTITUTE NAME's](#) it is **recommended / mandatory** to fill in a Software Management plan for research software projects.

Storing and sharing

This section describes where the researcher can **safely** store and share the data and software **during their research**. In contrast, the next section on [archiving and publishing](#) explains where to archive the research data and software for the long-term (e.g., after the research is complete or published in an academic publication).

Storing and sharing options

*Research data must be stored in an adequate facility where at least one other member of the research institute can get access. Researchers at **INSTITUTE NAME** can use the following options: [Radboud Data Repository](#), [a Microsoft 365 Team](#), [a workgroup folder](#), [SURFdrive](#), or [LIST OTHER OPTIONS](#)*

At **INSTITUTE NAME** the researcher can safely store and or share the data and software using the following options: [Radboud Data Repository](#), [a Microsoft 365 Team](#), [a workgroup folder](#), [SURFfilesender](#), [GitLab/GitHub/Codeberg](#) or [LIST OTHER OPTIONS](#). Each option is outlined in more detail below. When sharing data/software or collaborating, researchers should follow good **access control** practices, meaning that they should manage who has access to what, and who has viewing or editing rights. Data and software must be stored in such a way that, apart from the researcher, they can be accessed by at least one other authorised member of the research institute. This is to prevent data loss when the researcher leaves or is unavailable.

1. **Microsoft 365 Teams:** A researcher can use a Microsoft 365 Team to store the data/software during their research as well as collaborate with internal and external individuals. When creating and using a Microsoft 365 Team, the researcher **must** use their Radboud account, and **not** a personal account. Further, the researcher is **required / recommended** to disable the synchronisation setting in a Microsoft 365 Team. [SPECIFY OTHER REQUIREMENTS](#). Be aware that Microsoft 365 Teams and OneDrive are not the same. OneDrive is not an option for storing and sharing.

[AND / OR]

2. **Radboud Data Repository:** The RDR can be used to safely store and share data/software with fellow researchers (and students) at Radboud University and to collaborate with external researchers. Be aware that the RDR is not to be used for work-in-progress when multiple people access the same files simultaneously, as this could cause files to be accidentally overwritten.

[AND / OR]

3. **Workgroup folder:** Researchers can use a Radboud University network drive – [workgroup folder](#) – to store the data/software during their research and collaborate with internal researchers (and students). [SPECIFY REQUIREMENTS](#)

[AND / OR]

4. **SURFdrive:** Researchers at **INSTITUTE NAME** can use [SURFdrive](#) to store the data/software during their research and collaborate with internal and external individuals. Personal data **must** be encrypted when shared via SURFdrive. [SPECIFY REQUIREMENTS](#)

[AND / OR]

5. **SURFfilesender:** If the researcher is looking to share files in a safe manner, they can use [SURFfilesender](#). Personal data **must** be encrypted when shared via SURFfilesender. [SPECIFY OTHER REQUIREMENTS](#)

[AND / OR]

6. **GitHub/GitLab/Codeberg:** Researchers can store and share the software during their research safely using [GitHub / GitLab / Codeberg](#). [SPECIFY REQUIREMENTS](#). [SPECIFY WHICH OPTION is recommended](#).

[AND / OR]

7. **OTHER OPTION 1:** Researchers can store and share the data safely using [NAME OTHER OPTION. GIVE MORE INFORMATION.](#)

In case none of these solutions meet the researcher's needs, the data steward should be [contacted](#). Together with the researcher, the data steward will investigate the best solutions that fit the researcher's needs.

Prohibited/Non-recommended options for storing and sharing

Storing and sharing research data using the following means is **not recommended / allowed**⁴:

- **Personal commercial cloud drives** such as *Google Drive* and *Dropbox*. Commercial cloud services may be situated outside of the European Union and therefore other regulations and laws may apply to them. Further, cloud services may claim rights to the data and software that they store.
- **Commercial services** such as *WeTransfer*. These are not [recommended / allowed](#) for the same reasons as given for commercial cloud services above.
- **External drives** such as *USB drives*, *SD-cards*, and *external hard drives*. These are discouraged since they can easily be lost. If a researcher needs to use an external hard drive, SD-card or USB drive, they [must / should](#) make sure that:
 - they are encrypted.
 - the amount of time that data/software is stored on these devices is limited.
 - the data/software are backed up in a recommended storage location as soon as possible.
- **Mobile phones** should be avoided (e.g., as recording devices) for storage or sharing since oftentimes they are connected to a cloud and therefore not recommended for the same reasons as given for commercial cloud services.

Non-digital data

[Any non-digital \(research\) data \(e.g., hand taken notes, consent forms\)](#) **must be digitised** as soon as possible (inspired by the DIV and Archive Management Guidelines). Paper originals **must** be securely stored in a locked cabinet for six months, after which they can be disposed of. These six months give the researcher time to fix any issues, such as skewed, missing, or unreadable pages that may be present in the digitalised version. If it is not possible to digitise the paper documents, [or artifacts from fieldwork](#), then the researcher **must** store these in a locked cabinet where only authorised personnel can access them. [The one exception to these substitution guidelines is consent forms from WMO obligated research, for which the non-digital forms must be preserved for 15 years \(25 years in case of clinical trials\).](#)

Commented [HB5]: We recommend that you adapt this to the types of non-digital data that are commonly collected within your research institute.

Archiving and publishing

Research data underlying a scientific publication must be archived in a trusted data repository following the findable and accessible principles (F and A of FAIR).

Archiving and publishing are relevant throughout a research project, whenever research data/software needs to be preserved for the long-term, as is the case for research data/software that are relevant for the verification or replication of published research or expected to have reuse value. In line with the requirements of the [RU RDM policy](#), [INSTITUTE NAME](#) sees to it that archiving and publishing research data, pertaining to scientific publications are **findable** and **accessible** as outlined by the [FAIR principles](#)⁵. As specified in the [RU](#)

⁴ See "[Sharing and storing files safely](#)" where "Unsafe storage locations" are specified for sensitive data.

⁵ See [GO-FAIR](#) and Wilkinson et al. (2016) for a full overview of these principles.

RDM policy, findable means that the (meta)data should be discoverable by humans and machines. Additionally, the data/software are referenced with a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI or handle) and the metadata include the identifier of the data. Accessible means that it should be clear how humans and machines can gain access to data/software. Access should be possible using open and free protocols such as the internet. Metadata should be accessible, even when the data/software are not.

Having the data/software be findable and accessible ensures:

- the integrity and reproducibility of research
- the potential of research data/software reuse
- the recognition and accountability of the involved researchers

Furthermore, **INSTITUTE NAME** encourages researchers to ensure that the research data/software is additionally both interoperable and reusable⁶. By archiving or publishing the data/software in one of the **INSTITUTE NAME**'s approved repositories, researchers will be able to abide by the findability and accessibility principles in FAIR.

For the sake of **transparency**⁷ and **scientific integrity** it is vital that research data/software can be independently verified to exist and is described in sufficient detail to enable replication of the data collection and analysis. All newly generated research data/software that are required for the verification and replication of published research findings at **INSTITUTE NAME** must therefore be archived or published for a **minimum of 10 years** after the publication date of the related scientific publication. Research data/software must be archived and/or published in a **trusted data repository**⁸ in a manner that allows continued understandability of the data over time. It is encouraged that the researcher uses their ORCID to link research data/software. This ensures that all the researcher's output is connected to them with a single identifier, enabling FAIR practices.

This repository must be used to archive the **raw data in their original form**⁹ and the **processed and analysed data that are created from the moment of data acquisition to publication**. Archived or published research data/software **must** always be supplemented with sufficient **metadata**¹⁰ and other **documentation** so that the data/software can be found and the entirety of the research process – is sufficiently contextualised. See the **research and software life cycle** above. To make research data/software more FAIR, researchers can use metadata standards that are relevant to their domain. Some metadata standards for this field include: **INSERT NAME OF METADATA STANDARD AND LINKS**. The metadata **must** include a link to the related scientific publication, and should include a link to other related works (datasets, software/dependencies, publications, pre-registrations, etc.) if applicable.

Researchers should be aware that if they archive or publish research data/software with the publishers of their academic publications, this may give publishers exclusive ownership of the data/software. For this reason, archiving or publishing research data/software with the publishers of an academic publications is not recommended.

Commented [BHvd(6): Please note that interoperability and reusability are not explicitly required by the RU RDM policy, which only requires research data to be Findable and Reusable. Nonetheless, we consider it an integral part of FAIR and think that it should be encouraged as much as possible.

⁶ As is stated in the Radboud University Research data management policy (2026): Interoperable means "(Meta)data can be exchanged and used, now and in the future, across different platforms, for example by using open file formats. Data can be integrated with other data using metadata standards, ontologies, and controlled vocabularies." and reusable means "Data should be reusable by others. Therefore, the data should be documented and licensed. Information on the content, context, and structure of the dataset should be included. A machine-readable licence should be included, so that re-users know what they can do with the data."

⁷ The Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2018) mentions how transparency means, among other things, ensuring that it is clear to others what data the research was based on, how the data were obtained, what and how results were achieved and what role was played by external stakeholders.

⁸ A trusted digital repository has been defined in Appendix D of the Radboud University Research data management policy (2026) as: "A data repository is "an archival service providing long-term care for digital objects with research value". A trusted digital data repository has been defined as having "a mission to provide reliable, long-term access to managed digital resources to its designated community, now and into the future".

⁹ The original form is the version of the data that has not been manipulated in a way that would limit further analyses.

¹⁰ Metadata refers to descriptive information that facilitates cataloguing of data and data discovery. Metadata allow humans and machines to more easily understand and interpret data.

Archiving and publishing options

The **recommended / required** archiving and publishing location for research data/software at INSTITUTE NAME is the **Radboud Data Repository (RDR)**. The researcher **is encouraged to / must** archive the research data in their original form¹¹ in a **Data Acquisition Collection** and the research data **that is created from the moment of acquisition to publication** in a **Research Documentation Collection** (see **The Chart of Guidance**)¹². The data/software that are made available for reuse or replication studies must be placed in a **Data Sharing Collection (DSC)**.

OUTLINE INSTITUTE-SPECIFIC PROCEDURES FOR ARCHIVING IN THE RDR.

Other archives which can be used for the archiving and publishing of research data/software are **REPOSITORY 1, REPOSITORY 2, ...**

OR

The **recommended / required** archiving and publishing location for INSTITUTE NAME is **REPOSITORY NAME**. Outline institute-specific procedures for archiving in this repository.

Other archives which can be used for the archiving and publishing of research data/software **REPOSITORY 1, REPOSITORY 2, ...**

If the researcher wishes to archive or publish the research data/software in a different repository, they **must** first discuss whether this is possible with the data steward. Before the researcher can proceed to archive or publish the research data/software at this repository, the data steward will assess if it guarantees long-term preservation, provides adequate security, and adheres to the FAIR principles.

Prohibited archiving and publishing options

Archiving research data/software using the following means is **not allowed**:

- **Cloud drives** such as *Microsoft Teams, OneDrive, Google Drive* and *Dropbox*.
- **External drives** such as *USB drives, SD-cards, and external hard drives*.
- **Local servers** such as workgroup folders.

These options do not conform with the FAIR principles, impeding the findability and accessibility of data/software. They also do not guarantee the minimal retention period of data/software and some of them create risks for data/software loss or data/software breaches.

Retention period and reappraisal

Research data underlying a scientific publication must be archived for at least 10 years after the publication date.

Following the **RU RDM policy**, research data/software generated at INSTITUTE NAME that support a publication must be archived or published for a **minimum of ten years after publication**.

After 10 years, it should be evaluated whether it is useful to continue to preserve the data/software. Data/software should be removed only after careful consideration. To facilitate this evaluation, INSTITUTE NAME encourages researchers to document the reason for archiving.

¹¹ The original form is the version of the data that has not been manipulated.

¹² The definitions here are inspired by the **RDR**.

Access levels and licenses

Research data underlying a scientific publication must be archived as open as possible, as closed as necessary and under clear access conditions.

In accordance with the [RU RDM policy](#), the default for publishing research data/software at [INSTITUTE NAME](#) is to make the data/software publicly available, **as open access as possible, as closed as necessary**¹³. This means that, as long as there are no legal, ethical, or contractual constraints, research data **must** be published under **clear access conditions**, for which we encourage [CC0 / CC-BY / OTHER APPROPRIATE](#) license. For software publication we recommend [Apache 2.0. / OTHER APPROPRIATE LICENSE](#). Publishing research data/software as open access introduces the fewest barriers and thus maximises the potential for reuse of the research data.

While there can be valid reasons to deviate from this default of open access, these exceptions are limited to ethical treatment and protection of the privacy of research participants (when deidentification is not (sufficiently) possible), preventing harm in the case of sensitive information about companies or socially sensitive information (e.g. about specific communities), knowledge security, public safety, intellectual property rights of third parties or contractual obligations with research funders. In these cases, other access levels might be required:

- **Registered access:** If the research data are [potentially identifiable or pseudonymised](#)¹⁴. If the software is [INCLUDE EXAMPLES](#).
- **Restricted access:** If the research data are [INCLUDE EXAMPLES](#) potentially or directly identifiable or sensitive¹⁵. If the software is [INCLUDE EXAMPLES](#).
- **Closed access:** If the research data/software cannot be shared because [there is no permission, if the data are too sensitive, or if OTHER EXAMPLE](#).
- **Embargo:** If the research data/software are [INCLUDE EXAMPLES](#) being used for a patent or another publication then there could be an embargo [until SPECIFY TIME PERIOD: end of project / first publication upon which the research data/software is published / as specified in agreements with funders or third parties](#).

If research data/software cannot be made public, the related **metadata** must be made publicly available (under a [CC0 licence](#)) to ensure findability of the data/software.

Whether data/software can be published and what the most appropriate access level is, [should / must](#) be determined in conversation with research collaborators [and the data steward](#) before data collection/ software development begins. Research participants should be informed about this in the Informed Consent form so they can make an informed decision about their participation.

¹³ According to <https://www.openaccess.nl>, open access is a broad international movement that seeks to grant free and open online access to academic information, such as publications and data. A publication is defined 'open access' when there are no financial, legal or technical barriers to accessing it - that is to say when anyone can read, download, copy, distribute, print, search for and search within the information, or use it in education or in any other way within the legal agreements.

¹⁴ See section below on [Personal data](#).

¹⁵ See section below on [Personal data](#).

Registration

Registering published research data, preferably linked to the researcher's ORCID, is strongly encouraged.

Once a dataset/software is [archived](#) or published, it **should / must** be **registered** in Radboud University's Current Research Information System (CRIS). [This happens automatically if the RDR is used to archive or publish the data/software, as long as the metadata are made public.](#) The registration should use the PID of the data/software and link to the associated publication(s). Further, use of the researcher's **ORCID** is strongly encouraged. At [INSTITUTE NAME](#) this registration is done by [SPECIFY WHO: the researcher](#).

Research-related data

There are **other forms of research-related data** that are not suited for archiving or publishing in a repository but must be stored regardless. These research-related data include but are not limited to: administrative personal data that the researcher collects and cannot dispose of during the course of their research, filled in consent forms, applications and approval for ethics committees and grant providers, data/software management plans, and encrypted keyfiles that must be preserved for pseudonymous datasets.

1. These other forms of research-related data must be stored in a **workgroup folder**, in line with the following requirements: [SPECIFY INSTITUTE SPECIFIC REQUIREMENTS FOR FOLDER STRUCTURE, WHO HAS ACCESS RIGHTS, WHO TO CONTACT TO CREATE THE WORKGROUP FOLDER, ETC.](#)

OR

2. These other forms of research-related data must be stored in a **Microsoft 365 Team**, in line with the following requirements: [SPECIFY INSTITUTE SPECIFIC REQUIREMENTS FOR FOLDER STRUCTURE, WHO HAS ACCESS RIGHTS, WHO TO CONTACT TO CREATE a Microsoft 365 Team, ETC](#)

OR

3. These other forms of research-related data must be stored in **OTHER RU APPROVED STORAGE LOCATION**, in line with the following requirements: [SPECIFY INSTITUTE SPECIFIC REQUIREMENTS FOR FOLDER STRUCTURE, WHO HAS ACCESS RIGHTS, WHO TO CONTACT TO CREATE THE STORAGE LOCATION, ETC.](#)

Personal data

In the process of doing research at [INSTITUTE NAME](#), it is [common / occasionally possible](#) that researchers collect, analyse, or otherwise process¹⁶ **personal data**. This refers to information that can either directly identify a living individual or which, when combined with other information, can be traced back to a living individual¹⁷. Personal data can be present within the research data itself, but also in administrative data or in the information related to the informed consent process. Whenever this is the case, the personal data in the research becomes subject to the [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (GDPR). The researcher, in their role as

Commented [KM7]: We highly recommend that you talk to your faculty's local privacy officer (<https://www.ru.nl/en/contact/privacy-officers>) about the Personal data, DPIA, and anonymisation sections.

Commented [BHvd(8): There might be research institutes in which personal data is altogether non-existent or rarely used. In that case you can decide to leave the personal data and anonymisation section out altogether, or replace it with a more concise version.

¹⁶ The [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (2018) describes processing as any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.

¹⁷ According to the [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (2018), 'personal data' means any information relating to an identified or identifiable living natural person.

controller¹⁸, joint controller, or processor¹⁹ of this personal data, must be able to demonstrate compliance with this regulation. In order to comply with the GDPR, researchers **must** familiarise themselves with the GDPR, e.g. through courses, information provided by the Radboud University (on [privacy](#) or on [RDM](#)), or via the GDPR itself. The researcher is expected to take into account the consequences that this regulation has for their research throughout the entirety of the research process, from research planning to data acquisition to data publication.

This means, among other things, that data containing personal data can only ever be collected, analysed, or otherwise processed when a clearly defined legal basis exists, such as informed consent, public interest, or legitimate interest. Furthermore, participants must be made aware of their privacy rights, in particular the right to be informed²⁰ and the right to be forgotten²¹. Finally, when sharing data or collaborating, researchers should also follow **data minimisation** practices, meaning that they should only store and share personal data that is required for the research project.

Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)

The researcher is advised to / **must** contact their [local privacy coordinator](#) / [local privacy officer](#) whenever [personal data](#) / [special categories of personal data](#) or [other sensitive personal data](#)²² are collected, analysed, or otherwise processed. The [General Data Protection Regulation](#) describes the **special categories of personal data** as personal data that is related to:

- Health data
- Race or ethnic background
- Political opinions
- Religious or philosophical beliefs
- Membership of a trade union
- Sex life or sexual orientation
- Genetic data
- Biometric data

A Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) allows for an assessment of the privacy risks associated with a certain research design and determines what the appropriate measures are to minimise or avoid these risks. A **pre-DPIA** can quickly assess if a DPIA is required for a given research design. Whenever the researcher collects, analyses, or otherwise processes personal data, it is **recommended** / **mandatory** that a **pre-DPIA** is filled out together with the [local privacy officer](#) / [local privacy coordinator](#) before the data collection starts.

Anonymisation

Researchers are encouraged to anonymise the personal data in their research project **as much and as soon as possible**, as this effectively removes the personal data from the dataset and significantly reduces the privacy risks. If the researcher chooses to anonymise research data then this should be detailed in the informed consent. A dataset is considered anonymous if it is no longer possible to identify any of the participants in any way²³. To be considered anonymous, a dataset must not contain any direct identifiers²⁴ that can be linked to participants in the data, metadata²⁵, or documentation. Furthermore, the risk of

Commented [BHvd(9)]: It is currently not clear when this will be implemented. We recommend that you consult the local privacy officer to determine what would be a good time to include this paragraph in the policy.

¹⁸ The [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (2018) defines the controller as a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data. When there are two or more controllers the GDPR speaks of joint controllers and arrangements must be made to share responsibility for GDPR compliance.

¹⁹ The [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (2018) defines the processor as a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller. A processor thus carries out specific processing instructions and activities for the controller.

²⁰ More information on the right to be informed can be found [here](#).

²¹ More information on the right to be forgotten can be found [here](#).

²² Examples of sensitive personal data include (but are not limited to) personal data that is related to BSN numbers, confidential business data, confidential state security data, work performance data, financial information, criminal convictions, punishable offences, or illegal acts.

²³ The [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (2018) advises that, to ascertain whether means are reasonably likely to be used to identify the natural person, account should be taken of all objective factors, such as the costs of and the amount of time required for identification, taking into consideration the available technology at the time of the processing and technological developments. Using these means it may be possible to identify someone, for example through [the singling out of individuals](#), [the linking of records](#) or [the inference of information](#).

²⁴ According to the [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (2018), an individual is directly identifiable if you can identify them using nothing but the information you possess. This would for example be a name, photo, video or audio recording.

²⁵ See footnote 8.

identification via combinations of indirect identifiers²⁶ or via combinations of different datasets must be sufficiently reduced in order to make re-identification effectively impossible. When a dataset is anonymised it is not considered personal data and is, therefore, not subject to the requirements of the GDPR.

Pseudonymisation

Pseudonymisation²⁷, while not removing the personal data, is an alternative to anonymisation by which the privacy risks of a data breach can be reduced. Researchers should be aware, however that pseudonymisation keeps the link between personal data and the participant intact, meaning that pseudonymised data are still considered personal data and thus subject to the requirements of the GDPR.

Whenever it is impossible to effectively anonymise or pseudonymise a dataset, for example when this would result in excessive loss of relevant information, the identifiable research data **must** be archived or published under the conditions specified in the informed consent. Researchers must therefore plan under which conditions they intend to archive or publish the data prior to acquiring informed consent, so that they can inform their participants about the data archiving and publication strategy.

Ethics and informed consent

There are **CERTAIN CIRCUMSTANCES** that require **INSTITUTE NAME** researchers to submit their research proposal for review to the **NAME OF ETHICS COMMITTEE**. The researcher **must** consult the **ETHICS COMMITTEE WEBSITE** in order to determine if they need to send their research proposal in for review before they start with the data collection/software development. Further, the researcher must consult **ETHICS COMMITTEE WEBSITE**, for information on informed consent – when it is needed and how to properly accomplish this.

Commented [HB10]: This can either be filled in in line with the requirements set with the ethics committee, or left blank and replaced with 'certain circumstances' if these cannot readily be listed here.

Support and training

Contact information

The **INSTITUTE NAME**'s data steward can be contacted at **EMAIL ADDRESS** or at **PHONE NUMBER** if there are any questions about this policy for Research Data Management or any other questions related to research data management.

Training

The Radboud University provides a range of training opportunities to help researchers comply with this Policy and develop skills with research data management. The Radboud University Digital Competence Centre provides a **variety of workshops**. Participation in these workshops is **mandatory / strongly recommended / encouraged for all researchers / PhD candidates**. Upon request the Radboud University Digital Competence Centre can also offer **tailor-made workshops**.

In addition to this, **INSTITUTE NAME** also provides its own **workshops / information sessions** which are **mandatory / strongly recommended / encouraged for all researchers / PhD candidates**.

²⁶ According to the [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (2018), an individual is indirectly identifiable when you are able to identify a person by using other information you hold or information you can reasonably access from another source. Research data can be archived or published under the conditions specified in the informed consent. Researchers must therefore plan under which conditions they intend to archive or publish the data prior to acquiring informed consent, so that they can inform and obtain consent from their participants about data archiving and publication.

²⁷ The [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (2018) describes pseudonymisation as the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person.

Appendices

Appendix: Sources

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Appendix:

The research data life cycle

Research planning and design

In this phase, researchers specify the data to be collected in order to answer their research inquiry and devise a plan for managing the data throughout its life cycle. During this phase researchers tend to finish the study design, write a data management plan, and complete an ethics review.

Data collection and creation

This phase involves conducting experiments, making observations, doing interviews, conducting surveys, and acquiring secondary materials. Documentation of data collection, instruments and methods, along with information essential for data interpretation, is crucial during this phase.

Data processing and analysing

Data analysis is the phase where research materials are examined to generate insights that result in the research findings. The instruments, methods, code, or visualizations used for analysis should be documented and might need preservation for support of written or published research outputs.

Publishing and sharing

During this phase, publications based on data should include a statement indicating where and under what terms the data can be accessed.

Data archiving and preserving

Towards the conclusion of the research process, it is essential to preserve data that substantiates the research findings. Proper archiving of data in a data repository is the key to improved integrity and reproducibility of research and the re-usability of research data, now and in the future.

Data reuse

Data available for discovery and access can be reused by other researchers, either to validate original findings or to generate new insights. At this phase, the data may serve as raw materials for a new research cycle. There may also be applications for research data in policymaking, commercial product and service development, and teaching.

